

CCG In Vietnam
**Gender Equality
and Social Inclusion
(GESI) in Energy
and Transport Sectors**

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GESI VIETNAM REPORT, 2026

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Glossary

Energy system: A combination of technical (e.g., infrastructure) and economic systems (e.g., electricity markets) designed to supply energy services to end-users

Gender equality and social inclusion (GESI): Improving the terms of participation in society, especially for marginalised and vulnerable groups, through enhancing opportunities, access to resources, voice, and respect for rights.

Intersectionality: An analytical lens which examines how different social stratifiers (such as gender, age, disability, sexual orientation, refugee status, ethnicity, race, and income, etc.) intersect with each other and structural determinants (e.g., politics, globalisation, war, education) to create unique circumstances of power, privilege, and marginalisation.

Marginalised and vulnerable groups: Demographics of individuals who experience discrimination and exclusion (social, political, and economic) because of unequal power relationships across economic, political, social, and cultural dimensions.

Transport system: The vehicles, infrastructure, people, and logistics involved in moving goods or people from one location to another.

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1. Executive summary

The Climate Compatible Growth (CCG) programme works with partners in Vietnam, coordinated by the National Economics University in Hanoi, to support sustainable development with a focus on renewable energy and transport systems. Vietnam's low-carbon transition is unfolding alongside rapid economic and infrastructure transformation, creating both new opportunities and risks. While energy and transport investments are central to national development objectives, longstanding social, economic, and spatial inequalities shape who can access, afford, and benefit from these systems. As a result, the transition to cleaner energy and more sustainable transport does not affect all population groups equally and may reinforce existing disparities if gender equality and social inclusion (GESI) considerations are not consistently embedded across policy, planning, and implementation.

This document presents a condensed and revised version of a longer in-country GESI contextual report. It synthesises key findings related to the integration of GESI within Vietnam's energy and transport sectors, drawing on demographic analysis, policy review, and stakeholder perspectives. This condensed version provides an accessible overview of the current GESI context, highlighting cross-cutting patterns and challenges. This baseline understanding of the GESI landscape in Vietnam's energy and transport sectors is intended to support internal alignment, dialogue, and engagement with partners and stakeholders, and to inform inclusive, evidence-informed approaches aligned with Vietnam's development priorities.

Key Takeaways

- Marginalised and vulnerable groups experience unequal access to the benefits of Vietnam's energy and transport transitions, with impacts most consistently affecting women and girls, people with disabilities (PwDs), and ethnic minorities (54 ethnic groups comprise approximately 15% of the population). Predicted demographic changes will increase the relevance of older adults' unique energy and mobility needs.
- Across both energy and transport sectors, decision-making and technical roles remain dominated by men in urban centres, while women and other marginalised groups are underrepresented in leadership, policymaking, and skilled employment opportunities. Community engagement in planning processes is rare.
- Structural barriers related to affordability, safety, accessibility, and geographic coverage limit access to clean energy services and sustainable transport options. These constraints are most pronounced in rural and mountainous areas, where ethnic minorities are more likely to reside and where infrastructure investment and service coverage remain limited.
- Vietnam has established a relatively robust legal and policy framework addressing GESI; however, there is a critical implementation gap. Integration across energy, transport, and climate policies is uneven, and execution at sub-national levels remains inconsistent.
- The lack of disaggregated energy and transport data constrains evidence-based planning and inclusive infrastructure design, limiting the ability of policymakers and practitioners to respond effectively to diverse needs.

Sensitivity Note

This report applies a GESI lens across all relevant population groups. However, some topics are socially and/or politically sensitive in Vietnam, particularly LGBTQIA+ inclusion, gender-based violence, and sexual harassment. Researchers should proceed with caution when raising these issues, both to protect affected communities and to avoid inadvertently undermining relationships or access. Sensitive identities and protection risks should be discussed only in appropriate settings and with appropriate counterparts. Engagement with GESI should be demand-led, locally anchored, and guided by a do-no-harm approach. In practice, this means using trusted local intermediaries, applying careful informed consent, building in safeguards such as anonymisation, and avoiding any approaches that could increase risk or visibility for participants.

2. Introduction and background

Vietnam has made significant progress in economic growth, industrialisation, and poverty reduction over recent decades. However, systemic inequalities persist, particularly for marginalised and vulnerable communities. Women and girls, ethnic minorities, people with disabilities (PwDs), people living in poverty, older adults, and LGBTQIA+ individuals continue to face barriers that limit access to resources, economic opportunities, and decision-making participation. These inequalities are especially pronounced in the context of energy and transport infrastructure, where gaps in design and access limit the ability of some groups to fully participate in Vietnam's development.

Energy and transport systems play a critical role in shaping who can access employment, education, healthcare, and public services. Unequal access to these systems can restrict mobility, safety, and participation in economic and social life, reinforcing existing disparities, particularly for groups that already face isolation, discrimination, or financial constraints. Understanding how gender equality and social inclusion (GESI) considerations are reflected within these systems is therefore essential to assessing the broader impacts of Vietnam's development and low-carbon transition.

As Vietnam pursues carbon neutrality by 2050, a range of energy and transport policies are in place or under development, including the National Power Development Plan VIII, the Just Energy Transition Partnership (JETP), the Action Program on Green Energy Conversion, and ongoing carbon market initiatives. While these policies support low-carbon development, their benefits are not experienced equally. Factors such as affordability, physical accessibility, geographic coverage, and social stigma can limit benefits for marginalised and vulnerable populations.

This document summarises a GESI contextual report. It reviews the integration of GESI into Vietnam's clean energy and transport sectors, highlighting progress and ongoing challenges, and provides a critical understanding of the country's status quo. The findings will inform how to best engage with and contribute to inclusive policy development that is aligned with Vietnam's development goals.

2.1 Objectives

The objectives of this study are to:

1. Analyse the context of marginalised groups and vulnerable groups in Vietnam, including demographic characteristics, unique energy and decarbonised transport needs, and barriers to accessing these infrastructures.
2. Review national policies and legislation related to energy, transport, climate change, and GESI.
3. Assess the extent to which policymaking processes in these sectors are participatory.
4. Map key stakeholders working with marginalised and vulnerable groups and identify active taskforces related to GESI considerations.

2.2 Methodology

This study used a mixed-methods approach, combining a literature review, policy and legal analysis, and key informant interviews (KIIs). The review examined academic literature, government publications, and international reports to identify the demographics, needs, and barriers faced by marginalised and vulnerable groups in accessing energy and transport.

The policy and legal analysis assessed Vietnam's GESI legislation alongside sector-specific strategies and regulations related to energy, transport, and climate change, with attention to inclusivity, participatory mechanisms, and alignment with global GESI frameworks and benchmarks.

To complement this desk-based analysis, 20 semi-structured KIIs were conducted with government officials, NGOs, advocacy organisations, academics, and community representatives. These interviews provided insights into policy effectiveness, implementation challenges, and lived experiences of marginalised and vulnerable populations. Findings were analysed thematically and triangulated across data sources to strengthen validity.

3. GESI context in Vietnam

This section provides an overview of key demographic groups in Vietnam that experience marginalisation and vulnerability. **Table 1** summarises available population data alongside critical social, economic, and institutional barriers that shape access, participation, and outcomes. The groups presented below are not exhaustive, but reflect populations most consistently identified in policy, data, and stakeholder sources as facing intersecting forms of exclusion relevant to GESI.

Groups	Population / key statistics	Critical issues
Women and girls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 50.2% of population¹ Global Gender Gap Rank: 72nd (of 146 countries)² Hold 30.2% of National Assembly seats³ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Underrepresented in leadership and decision-making positions Disproportionate burden of unpaid care and domestic work reinforces inequality in household and labour market (exacerbated by lack of accessible public care services)³ Around 62.9% of Vietnamese women have suffered at least one form of physical, sexual, emotional, economic, or behavioural control violence from their husbands in their lifetime, with 90% not seeking formal help (due to fear of stigma, lack of information, or mistrust in authorities)⁴
Indigenous and ethnic minorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 14.7% of population⁵ 54 distinct ethnic groups⁵ 35.5% of households live in or near poverty⁵ 68.6% employed in low-skilled jobs⁵ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Likelihood of living in poverty is 3.5x the national average⁵ Often reside in remote or mountainous regions, with limited public services (healthcare, education, infrastructure, sanitation)⁶ Limited access to education and vocational training + region-specific linguistic and cultural differences restrict opportunity to stable employment; likelihood of working low-skilled jobs is 2x the national average⁵ Significant rural-to-urban migration in pursuit of improved livelihoods (where face employment discrimination due to social stigmas)⁷
People with disabilities (PwDs)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Over 7% of population⁸ 13% of households have at least one PwD⁸ Higher incidence among women, especially in rural areas 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Incidence expected to rise as population ages Households with at least one PwD tend to experience higher poverty rates than the national average Limited to no access to education, training, and jobs Women with disabilities face heightened vulnerability and reliance on low-wage, informal work
People living in poverty	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Various estimates range from 1.93% to 5.71% of households⁷ Higher incidence among ethnic minorities and rural communities (significant overlap)⁸ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Excluded from political representation and policymaking⁹ Often work as small-scale farmers or informal workers⁸ Lack of access to financial resources such as formal banking or credit (due to irregular income, lack of collateral, and limited financial literacy)¹⁰
Youth and children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 57% of the population (aged 35 or younger)¹ 10% experience significant depression and over 15% anxiety¹¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Play a crucial role in driving innovation and sustainability Expanding access to secondary education and vocational training in urban centres; rural and ethnic minorities excluded¹² Conflict between traditional norms and modern values surrounding gender roles and sexuality¹³ Limited access to mental health resources (due to stigma)¹¹
Older adults	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> 9.3% of population (aged 65+)¹ Proportion of population expected to double by 2035¹ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Rapid demographic shift due to declining fertility rates, lower mortality, and increasing life expectancy¹ Older women at greater risk of financial insecurity, chronic illness, and violence/abuse (due to gendered retirement policies and likelihood of living alone/widowhood) Downstream gendered implications: women are more likely to have unpaid primary caregiving responsibilities of older relatives
LGBTQIA+ individuals	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Official statistics are limited due to stigma and discrimination; estimated 3-5% of population¹⁴ 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Lack of legal recognition for same-sex marriages affects property, inheritance, and adoption¹⁵ Lack of anti-discrimination laws affect access to essential services such as education and healthcare^{16,17} Familial and societal rejection and isolation negatively impacts mental health; LGBTQIA+ youth experience significant psychological distress^{18,19} Significant strides by activists and NGOs in changing public attitudes in recent years²⁰

Table 1. Key demographic GESI groups and related challenges in Vietnam

*Note: Population and statistical estimates are drawn from multiple sources over recent years and are intended to provide indicative trends rather than precise annual figures.

4. GESI and energy

This section examines how GESI is reflected across Vietnam's green energy sector, focusing on different groups involved in policy, production, use, and knowledge generation. It outlines how representation, access, and participation vary across policymakers, the workforce, end-users, and development and research actors, and identifies structural and social factors shaping these patterns.

4.1 Policymakers

Marginalised and vulnerable groups remain significantly underrepresented in policy and decision-making roles in the green energy sectors in Vietnam. Leadership positions in these sectors are predominantly occupied by men and despite national commitments to gender equality and a just energy transition, structural and cultural barriers continue to limit women's participation in shaping energy policies and programmes.²¹

PwDs and ethnic minorities face similar constraints, particularly in accessing policymaking processes.²² Community engagement in energy planning remains limited, and participation is further constrained by language barriers, accessibility challenges, unpaid care responsibilities, and social stigma.²³

4.2 Workforce

Marginalised and vulnerable groups of all types remain significantly underrepresented as workers in Vietnam's energy sector, particularly women, ethnic minorities, and PwDs. For example, women make up only 21.1% of the total energy workforce: remote locations, unequal domestic labour expectations, and safety risks pose barriers to women's participation, although this figure is growing.²⁴ However, the type of role matters. Marginalised and vulnerable individuals are more likely to hold non-technical, administrative, and support positions, which typically offer lower pay and limited career opportunities.²⁵ These issues begin with a lack of educational and training opportunities, where marginalised communities remain excluded.²¹ Data on the participation of marginalised and vulnerable populations other than women in the green energy workforce is limited.

4.3 End-users

In Vietnam, marginalised and vulnerable groups face multiple barriers to accessing clean energy. While men are typically the primary decision-makers for household energy infrastructure, women are responsible for managing daily energy use and often rely on traditional cooking fuels, with associated health risks.²¹

Ethnic minorities face additional challenges due to geographic isolation and language barriers, which further complicate their ability to engage with energy service providers and access clean energy technologies.²¹ PwDs face inaccessible infrastructure and their unique energy needs are often not reflected in design, leaving them without the necessary assistive technologies or accessible energy solutions that would enable them to live independently.²⁶

4.4 Development actors and academia

NGOs, development agencies, and academia play a vital but often overlooked role in Vietnam's green energy sector. They connect underrepresented individuals with policymakers, advocate for marginalised groups (particularly women and rural communities), and raise awareness of broad GESI benefits, but their impact is limited by inconsistent funding, fragmented projects, and exclusion from formal policy processes.²¹ Nonetheless, initiatives like the Vietnam Energy Women Network, supported by GIZ since 2022, illustrate an approach focused on knowledge exchange, peer support, and professional development for women in the energy sector, while linking local actors with international advocacy and learning platforms.

Within academic institutions, marginalised and vulnerable groups remain underrepresented in energy-related disciplines and research on GESI is scarce. Without disaggregated data and field-based insights, it is difficult to assess how the energy transition affects different groups, especially in terms of access, affordability, employment, and health outcomes.

5. GESI and transport

This section examines how GESI is reflected within Vietnam's transport systems, with a focus on how different groups experience access, safety, employment, and representation. It considers four interconnected dimensions – access and affordability, safety and security, workforce participation, and data and evidence – to illustrate how transport systems can enable or constrain mobility, independence, and participation in social and economic life.

5.1 Access and affordability

Access and affordability of transport remain key barriers for marginalised and vulnerable populations in Vietnam's green mobility transition. Women in urban centres often have a lower ability to pay for transport due to gender-based income disparities, relying more on public transport and taxis than men.²⁷ Women also make more non-work and multi-purpose trips, such as shopping and caregiving; however, public transport is usually designed for direct travel, resulting in poor integration between different modes of transport and gendered time poverty.²⁸

Despite these constraints, women are more likely to own electric vehicles (EVs), as shown in **Figure 1**, reflecting different mobility preferences.

Moreover, public transport (public buses and metro systems) is not designed with safety or accessibility considerations, lacking proper lighting, ramps or elevators, designated seating, and tactile guidance.²⁷ These design limitations hinder women, PwDs, and older adults from traveling independently or safely. Instead, they are often compelled to rely on private or informal transport, which is typically costlier and less reliable.

Notably, there is no national network for electric vehicle charging; existing charging stations are few, isolated, and primarily serve electric bikes (e-bikes) and scooters operated by private companies. Consequently, home charging dominates, which excludes renters, low-income households, and those living in shared housing without secure charging areas from EV adoption.²⁹ Further, frequent battery replacements and high purchase costs limit widespread adoption of EVs.

Ethnic minorities are more likely to reside in geographically isolated areas (rural and mountainous regions) where public transport coverage is sparse and EV infrastructure is virtually non-existent. Current investments in EVs and related infrastructure are primarily focused on urban areas, such as Hanoi, Ho Chi Minh City, and Da Nang, with very limited reach into rural regions.³⁰

5.2 Safety and security

Safety and security concerns remain a major barrier to inclusive transport in Vietnam. Sexual harassment and violence on public transport, particularly affecting women, are widespread and especially pronounced during non-peak hours or in poorly lit and isolated areas.³¹ The absence of infrastructure that is sensitive to gender considerations – such as safe waiting areas, security staff, and reporting systems – undermines women's confidence while using public transport services, reducing their mobility.³² Further, there are currently no specific national regulations or policies addressing the prevention of sexual harassment or GBV on public transport vehicles or within transport stations.

Youth and children, especially students, rely on e-bikes, due to their low cost and the absence of licensing requirement.²⁹ However, supporting infrastructure, such as dedicated bike lanes, safe crossings, and bike parking, is limited.²⁹ These vehicles are often used without helmets and operated in mixed traffic flows, increasing the risk of accidents and injuries.

PwDs struggle with limited physical accessibility, lack of assistance, and poorly designed infrastructure that make navigating transport systems both unsafe and exclusionary. Similarly, ethnic minority communities, particularly in rural or peri-urban areas, may depend on informal transport services that lack safety regulations, reliable road infrastructure, or enforcement of traffic rules.

5.3 Workforce participation

Vietnam's transport workforce remains highly gendered and exclusionary, especially in green mobility. As in the energy sector, women are underrepresented in technical and decision-making roles, instead concentrated in informal, low-wage jobs with limited protections or career opportunities.²⁷ PwDs and ethnic minorities face additional barriers, such as inaccessible training and urban-centric investment. Young people, though major users of e-bikes, are not systematically engaged in workforce planning, with no clear strategy for training in EV manufacturing, battery technology, or charging infrastructure.³⁰ This consistent exclusion from formal roles in the workforce limits economic empowerment and opportunity, perpetuates inequality, and results in transport systems that fail to reflect or respond to marginalised and vulnerable populations' mobility needs.

5.4 Data and evidence

The lack of comprehensive, disaggregated data is a critical barrier to GESI-inclusive transport in Vietnam; without it, policies and planning risk reinforcing inequalities rather than addressing them. Most existing data focuses on broad demographic or transport usage trends; no national dataset exists on the nexus of mobility and gender, age, disability, or ethnicity and existing studies are often small, outdated, or geographically limited.^{27,29} A particularly critical gap is the lack of data on harassment, violence, and safety incidents on public transport. Ultimately, critical questions about how various groups experience transport – what constraints they face, how they prioritise safety or cost, or what services they prefer – remain unanswered. The absence of such data itself reflects the limited attention these groups receive in policy and planning.

6. GESI policies and barriers

Table 2 provides an overview of key laws and policies in Vietnam that relate to GESI across different population groups, summarising major legal instruments and their stated relevance. This table is not exhaustive; the full report includes additional policies and further detail on scope, responsible ministries, and identified gaps.

Vietnam has established a relatively robust legal framework on GESI, including legislation and strategies related to gender equality, disability, ethnic minorities, green energy, and sustainable transport. However, policy coverage and clarity vary across sectors, and references to GESI are not always consistent or explicit. For instance, while gender equality considerations are required for national-level legislation, they are not compulsory at sub-national levels, contributing to uneven application across regions – especially in rural areas.

Implementation challenges persist due to limited guidance, capacity, and accountability mechanisms, particularly at local levels. In addition, the lack of disaggregated data by gender, age, disability, and ethnicity undermines evidence-based and inclusive infrastructure planning. Where evidence does exist, gaps in GESI expertise can hinder its effective use in policy and research. Further, marginalised and vulnerable groups are seldom meaningfully engaged in infrastructure design, policymaking, or project implementation – those who could speak to the lived experiences and unique needs of diverse users in the absence of quantitative data.

Key Policies	Relevance
GESI	
The Law on Ethnic Minority Affairs (2001)	Provisions for the protection of ethnic minorities' rights, including language preservation, cultural identity, and access to education, healthcare, and public services
The Law on Youth (2005)	Framework for youth protection, development, and engagement in political/social activities
The Law on Gender Equality (2006)	Law for gender equality in politics, economics, culture, society, and family by creating opportunities for both men and women to participate equally in development processes
National Action Plan on Disability (2006–2010)	Guides the implementation of disability policies, focusing on social integration, accessibility, and empowerment
UN Convention on the Rights of Persons with Disabilities (2007)	Informs national efforts to improve accessibility, reduce discrimination, and ensure PwDs can participate in public life
The Law on Persons with Disabilities (2010)	Mandates equal opportunities for PwDs and requires that public and private sectors provide reasonable access to services and facilities
The Law on the Elderly (2010)	Codifies social protection by improving healthcare, covering pensions, and creating opportunities for older adults to participate in community development
Constitution of 2013	Explicitly recognises that 'male and female citizens have equal rights in all fields' and mandates the state to adopt policies that guarantee gender equality; also guarantees the rights of ethnic minorities and their participation in political, economic, and social life
The Law on Promulgation of Legal Documents (2015, amended 2020)	Mandates gender mainstreaming in the development of all legal documents and requires a gender impact assessment for all future proposed laws and policies
The National Strategy on Gender Equality (2011–2020 and 2021–2030)	Seeks to reduce gender gaps and enable women to participate fully in social life, contributing to the country's sustainable development
National Target Program for Socio-Economic Development of Ethnic Minority and Mountainous Areas (2021–2025)	Focuses on improving infrastructure, promoting economic development, and enhancing the quality of life for ethnic minority communities
Climate change	
National Strategy for Green Growth (2021)	States that green transition solutions should improve marginalised groups' access to green financing
Nationally Determined Contribution (2022)	Recognises the lack of gender equality integration among policy documents on climate change adaptation and the impacts of climate change on vulnerable groups
National Strategy on Climate Change (2024)	Decisions that climate change adaptation shall cater to the unique conditions and needs of vulnerable groups to ensure their safety and wellbeing
Green energy	
Approving the Scheme for the Implementation of the Political Declaration on Establishing the Just Energy Transition Partnership (2023)	Approves the implementation of the Just Energy Transition Partnership (JETP)
JETP Resources Mobilization Plan (2023)	Broad framework for energy transition projects including aspects such as employment, skills training, capacity-building, affordable energy, and community consultation
Sustainable transport	
Guiding the Implementation of National Technical Regulation on Traffic infrastructure, Assistance Tool, and Priority Policy for the Disabled Participating in Public Transport (2012)	Guarantees that PwDs are given support to access and use public transportation, including the right to learn to drive and receive a license
Law on Road Traffic Order and Safety (2024)	Mandates that road infrastructure include inclusive designs and solutions to ensure accessibility for disabled individuals
National Technical Regulation on Construction Accessibility (2024)	Outlines mandatory technical requirements for constructing or renovating infrastructure to ensure accessibility for PwDs (e.g., parking, signage, elevators and ramps, doors)

Table 2. Key GESI-relevant laws and policies in Vietnam

7. Key stakeholders

Vietnam’s transition to green energy and sustainable transport involves a wide and diverse set of stakeholders engaged in issues related to GESI. These actors include central government bodies, international organisations, research institutions, and local civil society groups that influence policy development, programme delivery, advocacy, and community-level implementation. A particular emphasis is placed on advocating for women’s participation in green energy projects and supporting women’s leadership in the sector.

Table 3 summarises key categories of stakeholders and provides illustrative examples of organisations and initiatives working with different population groups. The list is indicative rather than exhaustive; a more comprehensive mapping of 57 organisations and initiatives is included in the full report.

Group	Examples of stakeholders	Illustrative initiatives
Women and girls	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government agencies (Department of Youth and Gender Equality under Ministry of Home Affairs, Vietnam Women’s Union) International organisations (UN Women, GIZ) Local NGOs (Center for Studies and Applied Sciences in Gender, Family, Women, and Adolescents (CSAGA), Institute for Social Development Studies (ISDS), Management and Sustainable Development Institute, Vietnam Energy Women Network) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Integrate gender considerations into national policies and sectoral strategies Provide mentorship, leadership development, and professional networks for women in energy sector Implement community-based programmes and awareness-raising initiatives
PwDs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government agencies (Department of Social Protection under Ministry of Health, Association in Support of Vietnamese Handicapped and Orphans) International organisations (UNDP, Humanity and Inclusion, CSAGA) Local NGOs (Vietnam Association of People with Disabilities, Vietnam Blind Association) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop and support policies and regulations related to accessibility, inclusion, and employment rights Deliver disability rights advocacy and capacity development programmes Provide local services, awareness-raising, advocacy, training
Youth and children	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government agencies (Department of Youth and Gender Equality under Ministry of Home Affairs, Vietnam Youth Union) International organisations (UNICEF, Institute for Development Studies, Youth Employment and Job Creation Network) Local NGOs (Vietnam Youth for Social Development) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advocate for youth protection, participation in decision-making, and access to education and employment Provide capacity-building, job training, career counselling, and leadership development
Older adults	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government agencies (Department of Social Protection under Ministry of Health) International organisations (Oxfam, UNFPA, Age International) Local NGOs (Vietnam Association of the Elderly, HelpAge Vietnam) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Develop and support policies and regulations related to elderly care, social services, and pensions Advocate for older adults’ rights, healthcare access, and economic opportunities Provide healthcare and social services, conduct community-level advocacy
Ethnic minorities	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Government agencies (Ministry of Ethnic and Religious Affairs) International organisations (CARE International, ActionAid) Local NGOs (Vietnam Ethnic Minorities Union, Center for Social Initiatives Promotion) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Promote policy policies related to education, healthcare, and employment for ethnic minorities Advocate for ethnic minority rights/protections, cultural preservation, and economic empowerment Conduct research, provide policy recommendations, and support community-based and social enterprises
LGBTQIA+	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> International organisations (UNDP, PFLAG, ISDS) Local NGOs (LGBTQ+ Rights Network Vietnam, VietPride, Institute for Studies of Society, Economy, and Environment, community-based groups on Facebook) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Advocate for legal protections and anti-discrimination policies Implement programmes to improve LGBTQIA+ social acceptance, conduct research, raise awareness, and create safe and inclusive spaces

Table 3. Key stakeholders advancing GESI in Vietnam

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